

Basic Teaching Requirements For E-Learning For History For Middle School Students (From The Point Of View Of Their Teachers)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 06, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: October 07, 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Teaching Requirements , E-Learning , History</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13899645</p>	<p><i>The current research aims (to identify the basic teaching requirements for e-learning for history for middle school students from the point of view of their teachers) and to achieve the aim of the research, the researcher used the descriptive research methodology and the researcher chose a random sample by 5% of the research community, as it amounted to (74) teachers and schools by (36) teachers and (38) schools distributed over the six directorates in Baghdad. Then the researcher prepared a questionnaire for the basic teaching requirements for e-learning for history for middle school students from the point of view of their teachers amounted to about (64) paragraphs divided into four areas, namely (the requirements to be met in the teacher - the requirements to be met in the student - and the requirements to be available in the educational environment - and the requirements to be met in the curriculum) and the questionnaire included a five-scale consisting of the following alternatives (the degree of importance is very high - high - medium - few - very few . The use of e-learning is weak among history teachers and teachers and they do not have knowledge of the requirements of e-learning. History teachers do not differ in their poor information about electronic teaching aids, educational technology, modern methods and methods, in addition to the fact that most history teachers and teachers do not have full knowledge of educational virtual applications and platforms. Training history teachers and holding continuous workshops to train teaching staff on the use of electronic technologies and integrating them into the education process. Taking into account the requirements identified in the questionnaire and providing them in schools and providing a technical and administrative staff in order to raise the efficiency of teachers during the use of technology and employ it in the education process.</i></p>

Introduction

The first topic \ the research problem

Traditional education is the basis of educational science since ancient times until the present time, as it cannot be dispensed with because of its advantages that can not be achieved by any other education, one of its features is direct communication between students and their teachers face to face within the classrooms, it is the most powerful way to teach and transfer the largest amount of information and facts from the teacher to the students, and there is no doubt that most history teachers adopt this type of education based on Diction and indoctrination, as the history teacher believes that their students are unable to think, express opinions, put forward ideas, acquire information and access to facts on their own, which led to the weak benefit that students gain from the material as a result of the lack of knowledge of teachers on the means, methods and advanced teaching methods that keep pace with the era of globalization, but at the present time traditional education alone faces some difficulties Problems such as the dramatic increase in the population and the consequent increase in the number of students and the small number of teachers Qualified people, the huge explosion of knowledge and technology, and the emergence of modern electronic means that can be adopted in the educational process (Al-Badri 2005: 61-63).

As the rapid and continuous technical developments (technology) and the flow of information in various aspects of human and scientific knowledge and the complexity and difficulty of life led to the emergence of several problems, including the lack of a proper balance between technical development (modern technology) and social life, if it is difficult for the individual to adapt properly in front of the huge amount of devices Modern technologies and their rapid developments, and in order to find balance and TikkiIt is proper to pay the educational process more attention quantitatively and qualitatively by reconsidering the curricula, studying their objectives, scrutinizing their content and method, evaluating them, determining

the methods and means of implementing the curriculum and making it keep pace with the rapid technical developments (technological) that have made the world a small village and it is easy to obtain various information to instill the principle of self-learning among students and urge thinking and criticism of its daily behaviors, and interest in scientific research at various levels and fields of knowledge, in addition to The complexity of information and the failure to take into account the individual differences between students, as the teacher is obliged to finish the course at a specific time, which may not enable some students to follow it as quickly (Darwaza, 2000: 128).

Based on the foregoing, the research problem has been embodied in the fact that history teachers and teachers often practice traditional teaching methods without taking care of modern technologies and devices and electronic teaching aids without considering the provision of the simplest requirements for e-learning in the classroom as modern educational means to keep pace with the development of technology to activate the teaching of history and attract the attention of students and encourage them to participate effectively in the educational process, so we can determine the research problem The following question: - What are the basic teaching requirements for e-learning for history for sixth grade literary students from the point of view of their teachers?

Importance of research

Education is defined as an organized and comprehensive process aimed at bringing about changes in the behavior of the individual and preparing him for life and his integration into the surrounding society, and as a result of the rapid changes and developments at the present time, which included all institutions of society, including educational and educational institutions, which necessitated the need to reconsider the educational plans and goals, so education is looking for total quality in all aspects and contexts of educational science, including the curriculum (Al-Khawaldeh, 2013: 32-33), curricula are a tool of education in preparing students for life, so the curricula must be upgraded and developed according to the developments and innovations of life and become a degree of mastery and more comprehensive to keep pace with developments in the world, it is a set of facts and experiences planned in advance that are organized inside or outside the classroom to achieve the desired goals in the performance of students, so the attention of educational studies focused on curricula, whether old or modern, as an effective tool to achieve the goals of education (Talafha, 2013: 26).

And for the connection of the modern curriculum (technology) and modern technologies, means, programs and electronic educational applications have become a philosophy and a basic pillar of the modern curriculum, so many of the requirements that must be met for the classroom environment have crystallized as the climate in which the educational process takes place, as well as special requirements for students because they are a basic pole of the educational process and special requirements for teachers as they are the basis in the educational process and they are the ones who provide experiences and information to students and they are the ones who determine the learning means to be used Each has an important role and nature within the educational environment (Abdeslam, 2010: 7-15).

The aim of studying history is to obtain information that helps the individual to understand contemporary issues and predict the future, as it does not focus on accumulating information, but on students learning the way of thinking, the teacher has a major role in raising students' motivation to learn using modern technologies and teaching aids (Awad, 2010: 5-6) Therefore, he must identify those techniques and choose what suits his abilities, history is an important subject, especially in the preparatory stage, and his teaching should focus on the diversity of information provided by electronic and modern technological technologies, including the World Wide Web of Information (Internet), which is one of the priorities of the teaching process in the (era of technology), as studies and modern educational trends in education have stressed the importance of using technologies, means, applications and electronic platforms in the educational process and the need to provide special requirements for use The aforementioned techniques in the teaching process, so it became necessary for teachers to integrate e-learning with traditional education (Abdel Halim, 2009: 388).

E-learning has become an integral part of the lives of peoples in the modern era, as educational institutions in developed countries have not only worked to spread the culture of e-learning, but also exceeded it to focus on education and develop its skills according to the use of its applications and techniques and make them part of the educational process (Al-Atrouzi, 2001: 8), so its employment in supporting educational programs has become a goal sought by education institutions in most countries from Here is Iraq, especially after the Ministry of Education realized the importance of this type of education in the period of the spread of the Corona pandemic and made it part of the programs to develop education in Iraq and solve some education problems such as the large number of students and the lack of knowledge except through the teacher, in addition to the weak communication between students and their teachers, e-learning helps to provide sources of knowledge (information and facts) and the content of the curriculum in a way that attracts students at any time he wishes and accommodates the large numbers of students in the preparatory stage and facilitates communication between students and their teachers

through the platforms, programs and applications offered by this diversity of education (Nabhan, 2008: 128-129).

Despite the great interest in e-learning, educational institutions are required to accelerate the use of its applications and benefit from them, as electronic and technical development is accelerated and there is no room for waiting, in addition to that there are requirements that must be met in the classroom environment, teachers and students in order for us to apply e-learning positively, so it is necessary to pay attention to that technology and exploit it according to the development of society, and this is confirmed by many studies that came in this field in many Arab and foreign countries, for example, these studies The study of Al-Sharhan (2002), the study of Flake and McQueen (2002), the study of Al-Hazmi (2005) and the study of Khreisha (2011), taking advantage of all that development in information technology for the benefit of the educational process Trend towards the use of e-learning in the field of teaching, so the importance of this study is as follows:

1- This research benefits decision-makers in the Ministry of Education to make educational decisions that keep pace with the era of development and modernity, such as the integration of modern technology in the educational process and curricula and the provision of basic teaching requirements for the application of electronic devices and technologies in education.

2- The current study is the beginning of other studies and research in the field of studying the most important basic teaching requirements of e-learning and employing them in the educational process in Iraq.

Research Objectives

The research aims to find out the following: -

1- Determining the most important basic teaching requirements for e-learning for history for middle school students from the point of view of their teachers.

2- Differences in determining the basic teaching requirements for e-learning for history for middle school students according to the gender variable (males - females).

Search limits

History teachers in the preparatory stage and its teachers in the morning government preparatory secondary schools in the General Directorates of Education of Baghdad Rusafa (first, second-and third) for the academic year 2023-2024 AD.

Define terms

I.Basic teaching requirements for e-learning

-Knew by Moses (2007) "They are the electronic devices and technologies and electronic curricula that must be provided in the educational environment to use e-learning" (Moussa, 2007: 12).

- Procedural definition of the basic teaching requirements for e-learning

It is a set of technical requirements, programs, applications, electronic platforms, teaching aids, devices and equipment that must be available in the classroom, teachers, students and the curriculum to teach history for the sixth grade of literature, in addition to other technical and skill requirements that must be met by teachers and students to be able to use e-learning and benefit from its advantages in the educational process.

E-learning

Salem (2004) defined it as "an educational system to provide educational or training programs to learners or trainees at any time and anywhere using interactive information and communication technologies such as (Internet, radio, educational channels, e-mail, computers) to provide an interactive and multi-source learning environment remotely without committing to a specific place depending on self-learning interaction between the learner and the teacher" (Salem, 2004: 234).

-Procedural definition of e-learning

It is the use of applications and techniques of technology, the Internet, modern electronic platforms and devices in the education process, whether inside or outside the classroom remotely in the history of the preparatory stage.

The second topic \"theoretical aspects and previous studies"

First: E-learning

There have been many means of using "modern technology and electronic technologies" in the field of education, especially recently, so several electronic means and devices have emerged that can be used in the field of education, including what the teacher uses inside the classroom "such as the smart board - datashow" and other audio and visual means, including what is used for distance education outside the classroom such as platforms, applications, electronic classes and other applications that have been addressed by educational research and studies and have drawn the attention of experts and specialists in the field of education To determine the best methods for employing technological innovations in the education process, which is applied to it as "e-learning" (Ismail, 2009: 31).

E-learning is a creative and skillful way to present educational content in an interactive and centered manner around the learner himself and prepared in advance and easy to use at any time and place using the Internet, which provides students with a flexible educational environment and available to him whenever he wants (Al-Khan, 2005: 19), and studies have differed in their definition of e-learning as it is one of the modern concepts that have not yet been clarified in the field of education or because it is an educational type that requires the availability of two basic pillars, the technical and educational side, so it needs a teaching that combines the two sides to be He has a complete perception, plan and clear educational vision, some studies interpret e-learning as just an educational method used by the teacher by electronic technical devices that attract students and arouse their attention and increase the strength of their focus towards the material and some interpret it as far from just an educational method, but e-learning includes all elements of the educational process, whether inside or outside the classroom (Moussa, 2007: 280).

Types of e-learning

1-Asynchronous e-learning: - This type of education is based on direct communication and at the same time between students and their teachers in explaining lessons and topics and discussing research, and it takes place either inside or outside the classroom through means of communication such as virtual classrooms, as this type of education provides immediate feedback and direct communication between students and their teachers.

2- Asynchronous e-learning: - This type of education does not require communication between students, teachers and the curriculum at the same time, but it is self-education in which the student chooses the appropriate time for him through e-mail or pre-recorded videos according to a schedule prepared for distance learning "self", as this type of education allows the student to learn at the right time for him and chose the appropriate education for his abilities, but one of its disadvantages is that it does not provide immediate feedback from the teacher He cannot clarify an idea or obtain information from the teacher directly and needs a student who has a motivation and commitment to education (Faraj, 2005: 19).

Elements of e-learning

We can classify the elements of e-learning into the following:-

1- Student: - who learns either inside the classroom in which electronic devices are used as means of clarification and attracting students' attention or education outside the classroom through virtual classes and electronic applications.

2- The teacher: - Who supervises the e-learning process, whether directly inside or outside the classroom through electronic platforms and classes, and directs the educational process to achieve the desired goals and evaluate the performance of students, so it must have the ability and skill to combine the technical and educational side.

3- Educational content: - Any scientific material, lessons and topics that are presented through devices, technologies, platforms and electronic applications and are not presented on paper as is the case in traditional education, as the educational content in e-learning includes live presentations via the smart board, datashow, PowerPoint, or in the form of Word or PDF files, through which the curriculum is implemented in a more interactive and more realistic manner, which raises the attractiveness of students and their understanding of the learning material.

4- Educational services: - E-learning needs a lot of equipment and services that must be available in the educational environment, including electronic devices and means through which the lesson is presented electronically, in addition to the need for the availability of the Internet and training on the use of electronic devices and the use of applications and virtual platforms.

5- E-learning management: - Any system for managing e-learning through education platforms and applications, including follow-up of the educational process of duties, tests, documentation of curricula and follow-up of student learning, and these systems are either free and some of them are commercial.

6- Developing the educational process: - Monitoring the educational process and its development, evaluating the performance and results of e-learning, and determining the ways to be followed to develop e-learning (Al-Shaya, 2006: 79-83).

The importance of e-learning in teaching history

Many studies and recent trends in the field of teaching have stressed the need to use e-learning and its applications in the educational process to keep pace with the rapid global development in the technological and technical field, which included all areas of life in the current era, in addition to its contribution to solving some education problems, including increasing the number of students, supporting traditional education with interesting means of illustration for students, and eliminating the disadvantages of traditional teaching methods (Abdel Halim Others, 2009: 267) Thus, it became necessary for teachers to integrate these achievements into the educational process, and history is one of the subjects that can be employed e-learning in teaching because it has aspects that e-learning contributes to delivering to students easily and clearly, such as displaying maps and pictures by smart board or datacho and displaying

summaries of the lesson, which raises and attracts the attention of the demand for theAs well as presenting the course of the battles through short documentary films (Al-Shaya, 2006: 128), many studies have reviewed the importance and effectiveness of the use of e-learning in teaching history, including a study (Abdul Amir 2017), which confirmed that "e-learning facilitates access to historical information and documents and presents them to students, which makes it a focus for the attention of history teachers to draw sources of knowledge and integrate them into the curriculum as much as possible."There is no possibility of it and thus benefited them from employing it in the field of teaching history, and the presence of electronic libraries and their prosperity in electronic indexes and materials produced electronically such as images, sound, shapes and animation facilitated many of the tasks that fall on the shoulders of the history teacher by suspenseing and facilitating the educational material, and this creates motivation for students in addition to taking into account the individual differences between learners, to learn more in the simplest form and less expensive, and also leads to creating opportunities for joint cooperation between students and raising the efficiency of academic achievement for them because The modern study atmosphere is far from boredom, which is one of the most important reasons for the low academic achievement for the learner" (Abdul Amir, 2017: 76-77).

Requirements for elements of the educational process

The researcher believes that the requirements of e-learning can be clarified and detailed by linking them with the elements of the educational process, namely the teaching staff, students, curriculum and educational environment as follows:

1- The requirements that must be met by the teaching staff: - "The teacher is the cornerstone of the educational process, and perhaps we do not exaggerate if we say that the history teacher who has high skill and experience in the field of teaching and the use of electronic technologies and employing them in teaching is able to achieve the goals of history even if the curriculum is of a modest degree of quality and vice versa is true. Even if its curriculum is highly proficient, there are several methods used by the teacher in the teaching process" (Hariri, 2016: 313-314), and since e-learning has become a reality for teachers, it was necessary to clarify the requirements of those who carry out the education process and limit their role in e-learning to the following:

- Education planning, i.e. designing and preparing the teaching material electronically, as well as preparing applications in which distance teaching is also carried out and designing the curriculum electronically.
- Employing modern techniques and technology in education and using devices such as smart boards and others as means of illustration during teaching.
- Encouraging students to use electronic technologies, searching for sources of information and facts, and its interaction within the classroom as well, and guiding students to obtain facts electronically.
- Directing students to self-learning, searching for information themselves, and guiding them to reliable websites, which increases students' abilities to learn through the Internet and modern technologies.
- Designing the book or course electronically and adding some activities that depend on the Internet and electronic devices, in addition to using several methods such as interrogation and discussion, providing immediate feedback, identifying students' needs and justifications for e-learning (Al-Fayoumi, 2003: 13-17).

2- The requirements that must be met by the student: - The student is the main goal in the educational process and all these efforts are made in order to learn to be a successful student and keep pace with the rapid developments in his time, including the use of e-learning, so he must meet a set of requirements to be able to use e-learning and deal with its modern technologies, and these requirements include the following:

- The student's knowledge of the nature of the use of electronic devices and the method of their operation.
- Ease of student use, dealing with and managing e-learning platforms.
- The ability to search and access information electronically from electronic libraries and electronic scientific sites.
- The student has the desire to use e-learning and benefit from it and realize its importance at the present time.
- The student's commitment to the teacher's direct and indirect directives and taking into account the time allocated for education, as sometimes the student's dealing with electronic devices distracts him from learning.
- The student must be serious and committed because e-learning depends heavily on the student's role in the education process.
- The student's ability to distinguish between websites that are reliable in disseminating information and facts and to stay away from inaccurate facts in their content (Al-Jarf, 2001: 76).

3- The requirements to be provided in the curriculum: - The curriculum is the basic tool for the educational process, so the curriculum had to keep pace with the rapid developments and the era of

globalization, the curriculum includes all the experiences, information and facts that students acquire within the school such as classroom activities in the classroom and non-classroom such as the library, workshops and other activities, as Cunningham described the curriculum as "the tool in the hands of the artist (teacher) to form his material (students), According to his ideals (goals and objectives) in his studies (school)" (Al-Surti, 2009: 23), so any process of community development begins with the school curriculum at its first level of planning and includes the description of the courses or vocabulary of the curriculum "academic content" and the second executive, that is, how the teacher implements the curriculum using modern teaching methods and methods and trains students on self-learning and that it is the focus of the educational process (Abdel Halim et al., 2009: 507), the electronic curriculum is one of the modern curricula in teaching that need requirements that must be met from these requirements include: -

1- Electronic textbook: Any provision of the electronic school course in addition to paper and contains a set of instructions that refer to the vocabulary of the curriculum.

2- Curriculum tools: - Either they are illustrative educational means inside the classroom such as smart board and others, or means of distance education such as electronic learning platforms to communicate with students via the Internet.

3- Educational environment: - Any classroom that contains students with their teacher or electronic rooms in which students register to communicate with their teacher and determine the information that students study.

4- Identifying electronic sources: that is, the teacher's identification of sources and websites related to the curriculum, which makes it easier for students to search for information and facts related to the curriculum.

5- Student testing "feedback": that is, preparing the teacher for the quarterly, monthly and daily electronic tests, determining grades, providing students with feedback, and informing students of the test scores (Al-Surti, 2009: 23-35).

4- **The requirements that must be met in the educational environment:** - There are several requirements that must be met within the educational environment in order to apply e-learning in schools, which include the provision of the Internet and computers to browse programs and learning applications and the provision of virtual classes in addition to the regular classes, and these requirements can be divided into the following: -

1- Human requirements: - That is, providing a specialized cadre in the field of computers, software and educational applications, in addition to providing a cadre for maintenance and technical support for electronic devices, and providing specialized trainers to establish workshops and lectures to train teachers on the use of modern electronic technologies.

2- Material and administrative requirements: - Providing modern electronic devices and the Internet to browse educational websites and educational applications and designing e-learning positively (Ibrahim and Obaidi, 2018: 614-620).

Previous studies

1- Study "Ward2024"

"The extent of the use of e-learning platforms in the College of Education, Department of History, from the point of view of professors and their attitudes towards it" The study aims to identify the reality of the use of the teaching staff in the Department of History for e-learning platforms in light of the spread of the Corona pandemic, as the sample reached (78) professors and then prepared two tools to determine the extent of the use of education platforms and a scale to measure the attitudes of professors for this type of education and the researcher made sure of their sincerity and stability by (0.86) and found the weakness of professors' use of electronic learning platforms due to The obstacles they face while using them, but they had positive attitudes towards educational platforms (Ward, 2024: 1-2).

2- Study "Salahuddin 2018"

"The Role of E-Learning in the Development of Education in the Arab Republic of Egypt" The study aims to identify the possibilities provided by e-learning in primary schools, train teachers, use it, realize its effectiveness on the target group in the study, and identify the most important demands for the adoption of e-learning in the education process in Egypt. The researcher adopted the descriptive approach and the sample reached (300) teachers and promised a questionnaire and the study reached the following results E-learning has become necessary in the era of speed and technological explosion and students and their teachers must be aware With the skills of using electronic teaching aids (Salah El-Din, 2018: 2-5).

(Patricia-3Study, 2010 (

"The study was conducted in Carolina, USA"

"The aim of the study is to identify the effectiveness of the smart board in developing the academic achievement of gifted students in the fourth grade of primary school in mathematics and the researcher

used the experimental approach to measure student achievement according to the results of the unified exams of the state, the study sample reached (173) students from (6) similar schools divided into two groups equally studied one of the two groups using the smart board and the second without it After analyzing the data, the results showed that gifted students who used the smart board did not achieve significant growth compared to their talented peers who They did not use the smart board, and the researcher attributed this to the fact that the gifted segment hardly highlights the difference no matter how the methods change to the semi-independence of their own thinking and cognitive structure" (Patricia, : 2010 5).

4-Studyodell&kogen&schumacher and Dloge (2000)

"Internet Use between Males and Females among American University and College Students"

The objective of the study is to know the goals and objectives of the use of the Internet and the difference between the sexes with regard to the reality of the use of the network by students of American colleges and universities Follow the descriptive approach in the application of this study The sample of the study reached (843) male and female students from scientific and literary disciplines in eight American universities and colleges "University of Georgia, Hawaii, New Jersey, Lim Peterson, West Hawaii, Brent, World Island, and the Massachusetts Institute", the study found that the extent of the use of University students had a large Internet and there were "statistically significant differences between males and females" in the goal of using the Internet in favor of males and that there were no statistical differences for the variable of the academic year or computer ownership in the degree of use (Gardner, H. 2000: 4)

Commenting on previous studies and comparing them with the current study

- 1- All previous studies dealt with e-learning and smart board, while this study dealt with the basic teaching requirements for e-learning.
- 2- Most of the previous studies followed the descriptive approach, and this is what the current study used.
- 3- Previous studies adopted the questionnaire as a tool for research, and this is what the current study adopted.
- 4- The place of conducting previous studies is different, including a study applied in the United States of America (Patricia, 2010) and (Gardner, H., 2000) and a study (Ward, 2024) in Iraq and a study (Salah al-Din, 2018) in Egypt in the uniqueness of our current study by applying it in the Directorate of Education of Rusafa II Baghdad.
- 5- Previous studies were applied to different stages of study, some of which were applied to the primary stage, as in the study of (Salah al-Din, 2018) and (Patricia, 2010), and some of which were applied to universities as a study (Ward, 2024) and (Gardner, H., 2000 for the current study, it was applied to the preparatory education stage.
- 6 - The results of previous studies confirmed the importance of e-learning in the success of the educational process, either the results of the current study Vsnordha in the fourth section.

The thirdtopic \research methodology and application procedures

Research Methodology

Often determines the type of approach followed in any research according to the nature, dimensions and objectives of that research and may use more than one approach according to the requirements of the study, the researcher found that the descriptive approach is an appropriate approach for this study and is consistent with the nature of the goals it seeks to achieve, and defines the descriptive approach as "an approach that depends on the study of the phenomenon as it exists in reality and is interested as an accurate description expressed qualitatively quantitatively, the qualitative expression describes the phenomenon and clarifies its characteristics, while the quantitative expression gives us a numerical description shows the magnitude or magnitude of this phenomenon and the degree of its other different correlations" (Obeidat et al., 2005:191).

Research community and sample

The identification of the research community is one of the most steps of educational research that requires infinite accuracy on which the research procedures, efficiency and results depend and is defined as a group of individuals under study from which the researcher chooses a sample on which the study is conducted (Al-Nuaimi, 2014: 65), the current research community includes history teachers and teachers in the preparatory stage of the directorates of education of Baghdad Rusafa (first - second - third) and directorates of education Karkh (first - second - third), either the research sample we call the part that represents the research community or The model to which the researcher applies his research procedures and generalizes the results to a larger community (Al-Kazemi, 2012: 83) The researcher chose a random sample of 5% of the research community, as it amounted to (74) teachers and schools sample for her research by (36) teachers and (38) schools distributed over the six districts in Baghdad.

Research Tools

The researcher used one tool in her study, which is: -

- **Questionnaire form for e-learning requirements**

To achieve the goal of the study, the researcher adopted a new tool and designed the questionnaire form for the basic education requirements for e-learning for history teachers and teachers in the preparatory stage, and for the lack of a special list of those requirements, the researcher has prepared a list of educational requirements for e-learning that must be available, and based on what was mentioned above, knowing the basic teaching requirements for e-learning by distributing the questionnaire form and knowing the requirements that they need to provide in order for them to be able to adopt e-learning, Thus, it is one of the most effective research tools to clarify the opinion of teachers and know their most important requirements.

Questionnaire Design

1- The researcher prepared an open questionnaire and distributed it to a sample of history teachers and teachers, experts and specialists in the field of methods of teaching history, the exploratory sample reached (25) teachers and schools to determine the basic teaching requirements for e-learning necessary to teach history in the preparatory stage.

2- Interview with a number of history teachers in the preparatory stage and prepared the interview form, which included 8 questions revolving around the requirements of e-learning, and the researcher got some of the requirements mentioned by history teachers.

3- Reviewing previous studies that dealt with e-learning and benefiting from the results reached.

4- Reviewing the history books in the preparatory stage, the nature of their topics and the effectiveness of their application through e-learning.

5- The researcher's personal experience as she studied history in private preparatory schools, in addition to being a specialist in the field of methods of teaching history to determine the basic requirements for e-learning.

In light of the above, the researcher prepared the questionnaire form in its initial form, which amounted to (70) items for e-learning requirements distributed over four areas.

Authenticity of the questionnaire

The sincerity of the tool (validity) of the standard characteristics (psychometric) important for tests and psychological and educational measures that must be measured before the application of the tool, because honesty confirms the ability of the tool to measure the goal for which it was developed (Al-Munshidi, 2007, p. 32), and for the purpose of ensuring the extent of the sincerity of the questionnaire prepared by the researcher in its initial form and the validity of the paragraphs and the areas it included and the extent of clarity and comprehensiveness adopted virtual honesty by presenting it to a group of arbitrators in the field of teaching methods and science Educational psychology, measurement and evaluation numbered (13) experts and arbitrator, to express their opinions on the clarity of the wording of the paragraphs and their validity in measuring the goal for which they were prepared, and the paragraphs that obtained the approval of (85%) were amended and redrafted some paragraphs and deleted paragraphs that did not receive the approval of experts and arbitrators and experts suggested some paragraphs and were added to the questionnaire.

Stability of the questionnaire form

Stability defined by Al-Najjar as "the extent of compatibility and consistency in the results of the questionnaire if applied several times and in similar circumstances" (Al-Najjar et al., 2013: 140), stability is a prerequisite in the numbers of the questionnaire represents the similarity of the answers of the examinee when presenting the questionnaire to him after a period of time not exceeding three weeks, i.e. the accuracy of the questionnaire in measuring the goal for which it was prepared, the researcher was used to calculate the stability of the questionnaire in the manner of "test and retest" The researcher identified An exploratory sample consisting of (25) teachers and schools randomly from the research community The questionnaire was presented to the sample and after three weeks it presented it a second time, and the correlation coefficient was calculated between the first application of the questionnaire and the second application using the Pearson correlation coefficient, and the total stability of the resolution was (0.87), which is a good stability coefficient.

Questionnaire form in its final form

The form became in its final form consisting of (64) paragraphs divided into four areas, namely (the requirements to be met in the teacher - the requirements to be met in the student - and the requirements to be met in the educational environment - and the requirements to be met in the curriculum) and the questionnaire included a five-scale consisting of the following alternatives (the degree of importance is very high - high - medium - few - very few), and to interpret the data, the researcher relied on the paragraphs that got achieved percentage weights and the paragraphs that got a weight of less than 50% turned out to be unachieved either paragraphs Which got weights ranging between (50%-59%) show that they are achieved, but to a small degree, either paragraphs whose weights range between (60%-69%) are achieved to a medium degree, paragraphs with weights (70%-79%) are achieved to a good degree,

paragraphs from (80%-89%) are achieved with a very good degree, and paragraphs between (90%-100%) are achieved with an excellent degree, and Appendix (1) includes a final model for the questionnaire

Application of the questionnaire

The questionnaire was applied in two stages

-**The first stage** was the duration of the application of three weeks on an exploratory sample consisting of (25) teachers and schools who were randomly selected to identify the accuracy, clarity and linguistic integrity of the paragraphs, and the researcher began on 1/3/2024.

-**The second stage** is the application of the tool to the main sample of (74) teachers and schools in the Directorate of Education of Baghdad Rusafa II, the researcher began to distribute the questionnaire in its final form to the main sample of the research starting from 25/3/2024-4/5/2024.

Statistical Methods

To achieve the objectives of the current research, the researcher relied on the statistical bag (SPSS) in statistical treatments

1" T-test for one sample T-test"

2 T-test for two independent samples T-test for two independent"

3 Coefficient of "Pearson correlation coefficient:"

Fourth topic \ presentation and interpretation of results

The section includes the presentation of the results reached and their interpretation after processing the data statistically.

- The results of the first goal, which stipulated (determining the most important basic teaching requirements for e-learning for history for middle school students from the point of view of their teachers), to achieve the goal, the researcher "extracted the arithmetic mean, standard deviation and T-test for one sample" to compare the average answers of history teachers and teachers to the basic teaching requirements of e-learning and the hypothetical average of the questionnaire of (90), the results were as follows Table (1)

Table(1)

"Arithmetic mean, standard deviation, T-value and hypothetical mean of the resolution fields"

	Number of paragraphs	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Hypothetical average	Calculated value (v)	Tabular value (v)	Significance level
g ments	17	22.13	4.330	51	18.51	2	function
ments	12	17.67	2.841	36	20.82		function
um ments	21	25.91	6.758	63	25.43		function
ments the nal ment	14	19.70	2.670	42	16.71		function
n as	64	85.41	16.599	192	47, 81		function

It appears from the above table that there is a statistically significant difference between the average answers of history teachers and teachers to determine the basic teaching requirements for e-learning that were mentioned in the questionnaire and the hypothetical average in favor of the latter, the arithmetic average of the questionnaire was (97.85), which is less than the hypothetical average of (192), and the calculated T value was (47,81) Thus, it is greater than the dialectical T value of (2) at the level of significance (0.05) and the degree of freedom (73), and the data indicate the weak use of history teachers and teachers e-learning as a result of the lack of basic technical and technical requirements for this type of education, but they were welcoming the idea of applying e-learning, especially after realizing its importance in light of the Corona crisis and the disruption of working hours in schools, which indicates that a sampleThe research suffers from obstacles and difficulties in the application of e-learning, some of which are technical, represented by the lack of experience of professors and students to use technology in the education process in advance, the failure to guide and encourage the ministry to this type of education and the availability of training workshops and courses for teaching staff in schools to use technology in education, in addition to the lack of modern and advanced devices and means and their high price, in addition to the low situation of schools, which lacks the simplest service means.

2- **The results of the second goal**, which stipulated (determining the basic teaching requirements for e-learning for history for middle school students according to the gender variable (males - females), and to achieve the goal, the researcher extracted "the arithmetic mean and standard deviation of the male and female scores in the sample and the T-test for two independent and unequal samples" and Table (2) shows that

Table(2)

"Arithmetic mean, standard deviation and tabular T-value calculated for the resolution according to the gender variable" (male-female)

Sex	Number of paragraphs	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Degree of freedom	Calculated value (T)	Tabular value(s)	Significance level
males	36	3, 77	2.014	72	1.26	99, 1	0.05
Female	38	59, 77	2.020				

It is clear from the clear results in the above table that the history teachers obtained, through their answers to the paragraphs of the questionnaire, an arithmetic mean of (3.77) and a standard deviation of (2.014), while the history teachers obtained an arithmetic mean of (59, 77) and a standard deviation of (2.020), and the achieved T value amounted to (1.26), which is less than the tabular value of (99), 1) At the level of significance (0.05) and the degree of freedom (72), then the result indicates that the difference achieved between the arithmetic averages of male and female teachers has reached (65.0) is a simple and unreal difference as a result of random factors, and this means that determining the basic teaching requirements for e-learning is close between history teachers and teachers, but they differ among themselves in determining the requirements necessary for the application of e-learning.

Conclusions

Through the results and their interpretation, the researcher reached the following

- 1- The general level of use of e-learning is weak among history teachers and teachers and they do not have knowledge of the requirements of e-learning.
- 2- History teachers do not differ in their poor information about electronic teaching aids, educational technology, modern methods and methods, in addition to the fact that most history teachers and teachers do not have full knowledge of educational virtual applications and platforms.

Recommendations

After the results referred to by the researcher, she recommended the following:

- 1- Training history teachers and holding continuous workshops to train teaching staff on the use of electronic technologies and integrating them into the education process.
- 2- Taking into account the requirements identified in the questionnaire and providing them in schools and providing a technical and administrative staff in order to raise the efficiency of teachers during the use of technology and its employment in the education process.
- 3- Linking the evaluation of the performance of history teachers to the extent to which it uses modern technology and electronic means of illustration in the teaching process.
- 4- The Ministry of Education's interest in the reality of public schools and providing an appropriate educational environment that allows the application of e-learning.

propositions

In order to develop and complement this research, the researcher proposes the following:

- 1- Conducting a similar study in other disciplines.
- 2- Conducting an experimental study to find out the impact of the size of the study courses on determining the basic requirements for e-learning.
- 3- Conducting a study on the impact of e-learning for history teachers on students' achievement and attitude towards it.
- 4- Conducting a study on the relationship of history teachers' use of e-learning with some variables such as educational qualification, experience and the size of the courses.

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